

THEORY OF DEVELOPMENT THROUGH THE USE OF FICTION IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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In the process of learning a foreign language, familiarity with the culture to which the language being studied belongs plays a significant role. Culture in this case implies a set of codes that prescribe a person a certain behavior with his inherent experiences and thoughts. Therefore, knowledge of a foreign language always presupposes knowledge of these codes: the cultural traditions of the people, their material and spiritual boundaries of everyday social relations, their living conditions, realities, history, mentality (taking into account the perception of space and time, emotional state), philosophical and imaginative thinking, type of behavior, non-verbal communication, etc.

An important role in the study of a foreign language, taking into account its cultural aspect, is played by working with fiction - a corpus of literary texts of a given language. Familiarity with and study of foreign fiction is necessarily included in the educational minimum for students. And since the literary text is its basis, the role of the artistic text in this process is difficult to overestimate. Thus, a literary text is understood in the article as a separate, highly individual work of artistic speech, written in a given language, as well as an integral unit in a system of similar texts. And in connection with this, fiction is firmly entrenched in the foreign language teaching program, and its role in the language learning process is difficult to overestimate.

When becoming acquainted with the fiction of another people, students gain an understanding of the cultural codes that underlie the language and acquire foundations on which they can later rely when interpreting text in a foreign language. Understanding a literary text in a foreign language is the key to further successful mastery of linguistic and cultural subtleties and is a support in resolving aesthetic and ethical issues that arise when translating a foreign text into one's native language. A foreign literary text, thus, as a carrier of a certain model of culture, helps a deeper knowledge of a foreign culture, on the one hand. On the other hand, through constant comparison of the text with familiar, domestic realities, which contributes to a deeper understanding of the native culture. In connection with the above, it is obvious that a significant place in the successful and effective study of a foreign language is occupied by the

translation of fiction (both from a foreign language into a native one, and from a native one into a foreign one).

However, the experience of school teachers and university professors shows that there are a number of didactic problems when working with literary texts. First of all, this is the problem of a small volume of literary material: the use of fiction in teaching a foreign language is sporadic (irregular, appearing from time to time) in nature. Investigating work with literary text in a foreign language, some authors note that literary text is perceived by teachers as additional, auxiliary material. The question of adapting a text in a foreign language still remains open for students. Based on the experience of practicing teachers, we have formulated some questions that arise when using fiction in the process of teaching a foreign language.

Firstly, can a literary text be a component (integral) part of teaching foreign languages? There are enough arguments for and against. Let us first consider the arguments against working with fiction. Teachers often complain that working with fiction takes up a lot of their time, both during preparation and in class, and does not bring significant results. This type of work is ineffective from the teacher's point of view, since the results are distant and difficult to evaluate objectively. For this reason, many teachers refuse this type of work, preferring other forms of teaching. On the other hand, we can list a number of the following arguments in favor of including fiction in the process of teaching foreign languages:

1. Fiction can be a significant motivating factor in the process of learning a foreign language.
2. Fiction is a source of knowledge of the history of a people and its language, its culture and traditions.
3. Working with fiction significantly increases students' vocabulary.
4. Poetic and verse texts contribute to the acquisition of phonetics of the target language.
5. Even partial, superficial knowledge of foreign fiction and the ability to maintain a conversation on literary topics deepens the communicative competence of students, facilitates the establishment of contacts with native speakers, and allows them to translate them at a higher quality level.
6. The teacher's creative approach to working with fiction creates an intellectual and emotional atmosphere in the classroom that helps deepen relationships between students, as well as between the teacher and students, which undoubtedly contributes to the development of their personality.

7. Through working with fiction, the student is to a certain extent aware of the fact that often a figurative expression or often the entire context of a work becomes the sphere, the background of daily linguistic communication.

8. Knowledge of the fiction of other people creates in the minds of students a certain alternative in relation to the official unified culture.

In our opinion, it is obvious that the arguments for outweigh the arguments against. But, having agreed with this, we are forced to resolve some important didactic issues. Here are the main ones:

1. The willingness and ability of future teachers to use fiction in teaching a foreign language.

2. What exactly should be included in a textbook consisting of works of fiction? Should fiction be included in core textbooks or should separate books be published for reading? However, from the practical experience of teachers and authors dealing with this problem, it follows that the publication of an anthology will not completely solve the problem of including literary texts in the learning process.

3. If fiction is introduced into basic textbooks, what functions will fiction perform in the general didactic concept of textbooks and how will classes using them be structured? Should teachers develop methodological techniques for this or rely on their creativity and erudition?

All these questions can be answered only when the purpose and necessity of teaching a foreign language using fiction is clearly understood. Literary education in the native language forms its goals approximately this way: only the student's ability to communicate with fiction becomes the ability to read culturally. Is this part of the goal of teaching a foreign language? In higher education, undoubtedly, yes!

The future teacher must acquire the so-called "literary competence" (knowledge of the history and theory of literature in didactic transformation). Without this, the practice of using fiction in lessons for students is impossible. How are things going in the initial stages of training? In this case, the gradual mastery of the ability to work with foreign fiction is based on acquired skills and the ability to analyze fiction in the native language.

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